

Dancing Landscapes, Volcanic Breath

An artist's take on moving with a volcano

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ABSTRACT

This text aims to contextualise the video work *Dancing Landscapes, Volcanic Breath* and a broader artistic research project focusing on the supervolcano in Southern Italy known as the Phlegraean Fields (Campi Flegrei). Characterized by an ongoing bradyseismic crisis, this volcanic caldera, which is home to over half a million people, experiences slow ground uplift and subsidence accompanied by seismic activity.

Through dialogue with residents of Pozzuoli and Naples, as well as volcanology scientists, this work aims to deepen the understanding of what it means to live intimately with the challenges posed by bradyseism. Movement becomes a key investigative tool in study of intimacy with land and geological phenomenon. Moving camera gazes at caldera's notable craters - Lake Averno - believed by the Romans to be the entrance to the Underworld (Hades), active vulcano Solfatara, naturalistic oasis of Astroni, and many others. Movement becomes central also in looking at how human and non-human bodies move on top of the volcano. The area is rich in archaeological remains and legends, such as the mythological war between the Olympian gods and the Titans. They serve as inspirations in conceptual and aesthetic choices made in the film.

Keywords

Bradyseism, Campi Flegrei, Artistic Research, Volcano, Dance

1 Introduction

Throughout two years of artistic research by practice, entitled on *On the Land That Dances*, I have produced video works, held exhibitions and talks, and am currently completing a longer film about the Phlegraean Fields (Campi Flegrei) — a volcanic caldera west of Naples

undergoing a bradyseismic crisis. It is important to clarify that, as artists, we often do not produce figures or definitive conclusions; instead, we use artistic methods and conceptual thinking to expand scientific approaches and generate new insights into various realities. In my case - insights into intimacy with the land, the dancing landscape, and living through the bradyseismic crisis.

This text is written to contextualize the video work *Dancing Landscapes, Volcanic Breath* and the wider series of screen works produced in the context of this postdoctoral research. In the video works movement becomes a central conceptual axis and method to elaborate on unstable landscapes and a tool to explore the closeness and intimacy between land and people. Therefore, one can say that archaeology, art, architecture, science and geology — all are partaking in an intimate bradyseismic choreography of the Phlegraean Fields.

2 Bradyseism and the Caldera

The Phlegraean Fields is a volcanic caldera that extends 12 kilometers in diameter, both on land and under the sea. It is home to more than half a million people, as well as many animal and plant species. It is subject to a geological phenomenon known as bradyseism, or slow ground uplift and subsidence. Since 2005 [1], a positive bradyseismic crisis has affected the caldera. It has accelerated in recent years, causing increased seismicity (earthquakes) and a slow uplift of the land, reaching and even exceeding 1 cm per month. This gradual rise is changing the landscape of Pozzuoli. For example, some parts of the port have become inaccessible to ships, and new beach-like formations have appeared. This slow uplift reminds locals and visitors of the ongoing filling and emptying of magma chambers, gas movement and hydrothermal activity that is happening beneath the Earth's crust.

The caldera features several notable craters, including Lake Avernus—believed by the Romans to be the entrance to the Underworld (Hades), the active volcano Solfatara, the naturalistic oasis of Astroni, and many others. The Phlegrean Fields are rich not only in natural wonders—thermal waters, craters, and lakes—but also in historical heritage. Here lies the sunken city of Baia, the Flavian Amphitheater, and the market columns wrongly called the Tempio di Serapide - a natural “indicator” of bradyseism.

Campi Flegrei has experienced several similar bradyseismic crises in recent history, notably in 1950–53, 1969–72, and 1982–84, during which the ground in Pozzuoli rose about 1.7 and subsequently 1.8 meters. Today, some community members are concerned about possible displacement. They recall stories of Rione Terra, a historic area of Pozzuoli, where the entire quarter was forcibly evacuated within a day on March 2, 1970 fearing eruption (which never occurred). There were numerous other temporary evacuations, but the one of Rione Terra was perhaps the most painful as the quarter remained empty. Recent crises aside, records of bradyseism—likely its subsidence phases—date back to Roman times. Ancient texts describe difficulties in construction or continuing businesses, due water flooding new shops and buildings. Today, the ancient Roman city of Baia lies entirely underwater. This is due to bradyseism and the eruption of Monte Nuovo—the “new mountain” in 1538. Hence, the phenomenon itself is not new. But relatively new is our better understanding of it.

3 Eruptive History of Campi Flegrei

Since June 2023, scientists at the Vesuvian Observatory INGV and volcanologists in the UK have raised warnings about the heightened state of volcanic unrest at the Phlegrean Fields [2]. It is one of the best-monitored volcanoes on the planet and yet - the exact timing of an eruption, or whether it will occur at all, remains impossible to predict. Seismic activity, which reached a magnitude of 4.6 in 2025, keeps scientists, local authorities, and communities alert. To some extent, locals in the caldera are accustomed to living with volcanic activity. At the same time, they worry about negative publicity and its effects on their businesses—restaurants, hotels, local thermal spas, and the port. The seismicity also directly affects houses (the walls crack), as many are not earthquake-resistant.

Seismic activity remains the primary concern of the population, but the Phlegrean Fields has a violent eruptive past as well. Around 13 000 years ago [3], the Neapolitan Yellow Tuff eruption spread volcanic deposits across Naples and the surrounding area. About 39,000 years ago, the massive Campanian Ignimbrite eruption sent ash clouds over mountain peaks and is possibly linked to the extinction of Neanderthals [3]. The eruption’s power was comparable to tens of thousands of atomic bombs. Each crater in the Phlegrean Fields—Lake Avernus, Monte Nuovo, Astroni, Agnano, or Solfatara—is a lasting scar of these violent events.

4 Ancient History Passed Through Mythology

Some echoes of the geological events have reached us through mythology. The area of Phlegrean Fields is rich in archaeological remains from Greek and Roman civilizations. They created layers that mostly remain beneath our feet, with some ancient monuments blending into contemporary architecture. It is humbling to think that the people of the past walked the same land—though slightly different landscapes—and wrote about the same volcanic craters we can visit today. Lake Avernus enters mythology through the figure of Sibylla Cumana [4]. According to legend, she was a Roman priestess and used to tell fortunes to Roman emperors. She spoke in a cryptic way. Perhaps intoxicated by volcanic gases - she saw visions. The Roman poet Virgil immortalized her legend in the Aeneid, passing to future generations the story of Lago Averno as the entrance to Hades, the underworld, to which the Sibylla would lead. Entering Hades was easy—it was always open. It was returning from it that was hard. Sibylla’s immortality was granted by the god Apollo, but she has forgotten to ask for eternal youth. Hence, subjected to permanent decay, she shrank throughout the centuries, growing smaller and smaller until only her voice persisted. They say it can still be heard today. Maybe it is a volcanic roar? The volcano roars every so often, before a seismic swarm.

Indeed, living on a caldera, rich in thermal spots and stunning panoramas, comes at a price. The Phlegrean Fields literally means “burning fields.” Phlegrea is another name for Gaia, the mother of the Titans. It is believed that the caldera may have been one of the locations of the mythical ten-year war known as the Titanomachy [5]. Zeus, saved from his father Cronus,

freed his siblings and rebelled against the rule of the Titans—sons of the primordial deities Uranus (the Sky) and Gaia (the Earth). The Olympian gods won the battle. The Titans were punished, with one of them, Typhon, being forever chained under the Island of Ischia. He is still alive, and trying to free himself, he causes the earth to shake. In this way, the experiences of bradyseism and volcanism from the past are transmitted to the future. They speak of something colossal, gigantic, and certainly bigger than human.

5 Other Artists Who Have Been There

Art in Naples and the Phlegrean Fields is inseparable from the history of volcanology. Sir William Hamilton, a diplomat and early volcanologist, made significant contributions to the understanding of volcanic activity in Italy during the 18th century. His work was closely accompanied by Pietro Fabris, an aquarellist who, under Hamilton's commission, produced detailed documentation of volcanic landscapes and rocks [11]. These works were published in the manual *Campi Phlegraei: Observations on the Volcanos of the Two Sicilies as They Have Been Communicated to the Royal Society of London*. Fabris's art was revolutionary: it combined scientific accuracy with artistic expression [11]. Until then, representations of volcanoes had been rather romanticized and simplified. Such precise drawings inspired scientific curiosity and served as important records of volcanic activity at the time.

Yellow Tuff enters art via an essay written by Walter Benjamin and Asja Lācis, a Latvian theater director and avant-garde figure. In 1925, reflecting on the social structures and the porousness of the city of Naples, they point to the main construction material—Tuffo Giallo—a volcanic rock produced in a violent eruption at Campi Flegrei [9]. This essay became one of the seminal works in the context of the Critical Theory developed by the Frankfurt School [5], comparing the societal structures of Naples to the porous volcanic rock that constituted much of the city's building material.

Two other important cinematic works were made in Pozzuoli by Giuseppe M. Gaudino in 1991 and 1997. They address the bradyseism of the 1980s—the films *Calcinacci* [6] and *Giro di Lune tra Terra e Mare* [7]. These films explore realities of Pozzuoli amid another bradyseismic crisis, weaving together local mythologies and documentary elements. They address relocation,

seismic experiences, local economic challenges, and the relationship between ancient architecture and its ruins. These low-budget projects are labors of love by a director who himself comes from Pozzuoli.

In 2022, Emilija Škarnulytė, an artist and filmmaker who is also a dear friend, made the film *Sunken Cities* [10], which captures the submerged city of Baia. The main protagonist, a mermaid, dives into the waters that cover the archaeological site—once the fascinating Roman city of Baia. Merging mythology and archaeology, the film raises questions about the Anthropocene, human traces, and the intersection of past and future life. These are just a few examples—among many more, of course—of how artists have attempted to document, conceptualize, or research Campi Flegrei and its geological legacy through art.

6 Approach to Research

Triggered by a personal loss, this project primarily, explores landscape as the body and body as a landscape. Using the movement of the human and camera bodies to rethink geological movements and instabilities, the project aims to re-evaluate assumptions about what it means to live on one of the Earth's supervolcanoes. From early stages of the research there was an effort to identify and explore different ways of looking at the volcano - via thermographic camera lens, used in volcanology science, VHS, Super 8, and digital - which all have time imprinted, just like rock formations. Super 8 was technology used during the bradyseismic crisis in the 60s and 70s. VHS was a dominant filmmaking technology in the 80s, during the second bradyseismic crisis. Using various textures of video in this research allowed to draw parallels between the time imprint of the rock and the medium. Digital cameras have their own unique textures and resolutions, which serve as a time--print of our era. The Phlegrean Fields are best perceived from space, so drone and satellite technologies provide a far more comprehensive perspective on the volcanic caldera—the film's main subject—than the human eye perspective. Both have their relevance though - the aerial view loosely references the Titans and the ground-level gaze refers back to those who imagine them. The video incorporates excerpts from improvisation workshops with Neapolitan dancers, who were prompted to seek patterns—as pattern seeking is an inherent trait of the human mind used to understand the world. The soundscapes were generated reflecting the legacy of Sybilla and using voice as a main instrument. The spinning columns of the Tempio di

Serapide, an ancient marketplace, is where the convergence of rock, living matter, human history, and geology happens.

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